
WATER TECHNOLOGY COMPANY CLASSIFICATION

01.26.23 - VERSION 9

The Water Council (TWC) has been taking the lead in Wisconsin on organizing its existing strength in creating solutions to the water quality and quantity problems that are increasingly found in the United States and world. TWC started and remains largely a sub-state organization in terms of its membership. But it is now engaged globally, seeking to help others solve water problems as well as develop Milwaukee business to global business and government partnerships.

TWC considers that any true water technology cluster requires the following collective strong assets:

- An existing core of water technology companies (spelled out below);
- Academia for research (e.g., agricultural economics, bioscience, ecology, engineering, freshwater sciences, genomics, policy analysis, soil science, urban planning, and watershed management) and talent development;
- A talent pipeline
- Innovative water and wastewater utilities (these are seldom water tech organizations);
- Non-profit organizations that offer a perspective on larger environmental and water issues as well as a broader method of addressing water issues;
- Multinational water companies with local operations;
- Entrepreneurs developing new technologies; and
- A larger community for understanding and support.

This paper contains TWC's comprehensive definition of water technology companies. The emphasis is placed strictly on companies that create solutions for water users and communities located across the world. TWC does not consider water users or water-related products, services, industries, and sub-sectors as being businesses within a water technology cluster. This list is intended to define water technology, educate others on this definition, and showcase the current strengths of Milwaukee's water technology cluster. *Warning: this list is not totally comprehensive; it can and will be adjusted to capture new developments in the field of water technology solutions.*

1. Residential Water Treatment Components & Systems

Point-of-use to municipal scale, including:

Point-of-use systems, 333318

Controls, 334512, 335314

Chemicals: 325998

Filters: 333318 and 333999

Membranes: 326199

Sensors: 334519

Ultraviolet Disinfection: 333318

Natural treatments: 325199

And other technologies, including ceramic microfiltration (333318), to identify and treat micro-constituents;

New technologies to enhance water reuse techniques at varying scales: TBD

2. Water Distribution Systems

Products used to inform and improve drinking water distribution. Examples include:

meters: 334514

High-tech pipe: 326122

Sensors to monitor both quantity and quality of water at multiple points in the system to detect leaks of various sizes, to judge pressure and help provide the ability to change pressures in specific sections of the system: 334519

Pipe monitors and repair techniques for varying sizes and conditions and related products: 334519

Valves for water works systems: 332911

Water security technologies: 334519

3. Industrial Water Treatment Components & Systems

Industry specific mechanisms of treating water for various reasons before or after specific uses, such as for food and beverage making or particular manufacturing processes such as metal plating or microchip making;

Pure Water production technologies: 333318 and all other NAICS for #1 water treatment Boiler water treatment, cooling water treatment, scaling and corrosion prevention and remediation, and related applications: 333318 and all of #1

Also ballast water detection and treatment: 333249

4. Industrial Water Process Systems

Systems for the movement (not treatment) of water, such as:

Irrigation systems: 333111; 333911

Fluid process and liquid handling: 334513 Fluidic devices, circuits, and systems for **process** control, manufacturing

5. Desalination Components & Systems

Water treatment systems and components targeted explicitly at desalination. This includes; 333318; 326199; 332410; others TBD to cover all below

Reverse osmosis treatment,

Forward osmosis treatment,
Distillation,
Seawater greenhouse,
Solar desalination,
Low temperature thermal desalination,
Low-energy electrodialysis:
Thermionic and other techniques and specific elements required, such as
Plastics: 326199
And biometric or nano-tube membranes 325199
And related elements of these systems: TBD
Low fouling reverse osmosis elements: TBD
Also brine management: TBD

6. Wastewater Treatment Systems & Components

- a) Industrial** – serving specific industry needs for reuse or for meeting Sewerage Systems standards for disposal into the systems; examples include dairy, fracking, food processing, metal plating, etc. to remove chemical, metal and biological contaminants, nutrients, heat, and other elements of waste streams.
NAICS include: 333318; 333249; 335314;
- b) Municipal** – Systems serving small to large scale public systems, some of which are similar for both scales of system but many of which are unique to one or the other system: NAICS include 333318; 333249; 325998; 335314;
- c) Components for Systems**
Aeration: 333249
Chemicals: 325998
Centrifuges: 333999
Controls: 335314
Corrosion protection: 325998 Inhibitors (e.g., corrosion, oxidation, polymerization) manufacturing
Disinfection techniques: 333318
Dryers (sludge): 333249
Bioengineered treatment: 333249
Gene-based pathogen removal, and the like: TBD
Sensors: 334519
Sewer pipe monitors – both visual systems and microelectronic: 334519
Source monitors: 334519
Outfall monitors: 334519
Pipe leak detection: 334519
Repair and replacement methods: 326199; TBD
Sewage quality management tools, and the like: 334519; TBD

7. Wastewater Resource Recovery Systems & Components

Ranging in size from point-of-use to municipal scale technologies to recover energy

Anaerobic digesters: 333249; 333318;

Hydrogen/bacteria/algae power plants, and the like: TBD

Heat: 333415

And nutrients (e.g., phosphorous, nitrogen, and other elements) and other resources:
333318

8. Storm Water Collection, Treatment & Reduction Components & Management Systems

Collection point treatment (manhole): 333318

Prediction (rainfall, surface absorption rates, drainage modeling, etc.) 511210

Real-time monitoring: 334519

Time delay mechanisms (green/blue roofs, lateral linings (326122), porous pavements, 327330 (porous pavement blocks); 325314 (compost manufacturing: soil amendments)

And methods of handling storm water designed by specialized architectural and engineering firms focusing on storm water at smaller scales related to NAICS 511210; 541330; 541620;

9. Water Harvesting Components and Systems

This includes mechanisms for collecting, monitoring, moving, storing (e.g., cisterns - 332420 [metal]), and treating storm water at a scale that varies from house to residential lot to neighborhood to specific use (e.g., golf course, aquaponics,) private and community gardens.

Collection system and materials 326122

Treatment: 325199; 325998; 333249; 333318; 333999; 334290; 333911

10. Water/Energy Use Efficiency Components & Systems

Tools and techniques to reduce water use and loss rates in settings that range from the home to large buildings to industry, agriculture, electric utilities as well as water utilities.

Examples include:

Monitors: 334519

Phone apps: 334519

Sensors: 334519

Plumbing fixtures: 332913; 332999

Garbage disposals: 335228

Clothes washers: 335224

Air cooling systems: 333415

As well as manufacturing processes.

In agriculture this includes:

Smart irrigation through monitoring soil moisture: 334290

Time of application: 334290
Method of application: 334290
Well monitoring, etc.: 334519
Among utilities this includes
New hydro-generation techniques for electricity: 333611 Water turbines manufacturing
As well as increased water use efficiency for dams and other hydro sources of power:
541330.

11. Water System Products: Non-mechanical, not covered in other categories

Products such as
Tanks & Boilers: 332410 & 332420 (metal tanks)
Fittings and Valves: 332911
Pipe Inspection Tools: 334519
Pipe Repair Tools: 326199
System Fabrication Services: 333999

12. Water System Products: Mechanical, not covered in other categories

Complete mechanical equipment (not parts) such as
Dehumidifiers: 333414
Aerators: 333249
Pumps: 333911
Motors: 335312

13. Engineering/Planning/Services/Consultants for Water, Wastewater, Storm water, Water Harvesting, Sustainable Practices, and the like

Non-manufacturing support services include:
Design: 541320; 541330; 541620
Engineering: 541330
Surveying: 541370:
Laboratories: 541380 to create better solutions for water and water/energy problems.

14. Aquaculture Components & Systems

Parts and systems for industrial scale fish and crustacean growing that include
Water monitoring and response systems: 334519
Water treatment: 333318
Tanks: 326199
Fish food, and related products (311119 Fish food for feeding fish manufacturing)
As well as similar systems and components to be included in aquaponic systems.

15. Well Monitoring Systems

Sensors: 334519

Smart system components to report in real time on water quantity and quality in a single well or in multiple wells used for residential, agricultural, or commercial use: 334519

I 6. Digital Solutions for water/wastewater/industrial optimization including AI (Artificial Intelligence), SaaS (Software as a Service), Telemetry, and IoT (Internet of Things). This includes collection, usage, processing and interpreting of data from disparate sources (sensors, SCADA, other operational data) to create enhanced insights for users on a variety of water system variables. Includes digital hardware/software systems/solutions for leak detection, water/energy optimization, smart water management systems, digital twin solutions, water quality, other.

Software Publishers 513210

Computer System Design Services 541512

Engineering Services 541330

Sensors (as a complement to software/digital IoT solutions) 334519

Computer System Design and related 541512

Research and Development in the Physical, Engineering, and Life Sciences (except Nanotechnology and Biotechnology) 541715

Non-classified establishments categorizing their scope as digital/SaaS/AI or service to water system users.

Examples of **NOT** water technology companies:

I 7. Maintenance Equipment & Services

I 8. Distributors of Water Industry Products

I 9. Well Services & Products - All businesses with a major focus toward the water well industry

20. Large water users – they are technology users, not creators